

AN EXPERIMENTAL AND FINITE ELEMENT STUDY OF THE LONGITUDINAL BENDING BEHAVIOR OF T-JOINTS IN VEHICLE STRUCTURES

G. Belingardi, E.G Koricho*

Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Politecnico Di Torino , Torino, Italy

* Corresponding author: ermias.koricho@polito.it

Web page: <http://www.polito.it>

1. Abstract

The behaviour of carbon/epoxy composite T-joint located on B-pillar is investigated using experimental and numerical methods. Detailed manufacturing process and experimental design factors are analyzed to understand their implications on the performance of T-joint structure. Material characterizations, such as tensile, compressive and shear tests, have been performed to obtain essential mechanical properties for numerical simulation. Experimental bending tests have been performed on structure prototypes. Commercially available FE software has been used to develop a numerical model of composite T-joint. Results show that numerical stress distribution and failure regions are reasonably in a good agreement with experimental results.

2. Introduction

Nowadays there is a considerable increase in oil insecurity, geopolitical rivalry among vehicle manufacturers, price volatility in materials for fabricating most structural components of automobiles and environmental change due to gas emissions. These issues coupled with the desire to improve the vehicle fuel consumption efficiency stimulate the idea of weight reduction in both automobile and aerospace sectors [1]. About 1% of the fuel energy is used to move the driver, which is the prime function of the car while 67-75% of the fuel use is vehicle weight related. The urge of making the vehicle much lighter has become the automakers driving force[2].

There are two main approaches to achieve lightweight vehicle structure: structural optimization and material substitutions. Researches show that structural optimization can give up to 7% weight reduction. On the other hand, material replacement

such as full aluminium body can lead to weight reduction up to 50%, [3,4]. As an alternative, composite materials have been recently considered as one of the key potential candidate solution to achieve lightweight vehicle structure regardless of its manufacturing cost. Beside, fiber reinforced materials have good corrosion resistance, impact cushion, noise attenuation and allow for relevant part consolidation.

Taking in to consideration huge potentials applications and benefits of composite materials in automotive body structures, a number of automotive industries, such as FIAT [5], Hypercar [6] and Ford [7], have developed prototypes in order to experience the use of composite materials for primary structures. Hypercar [6] designed and produced carbon-fiber body structures of Revolution vehicle model. The Revolution 187 kg body structure was 57% lighter than a conventional steel body structure of the same size, while provided superior crash protection, improved stiffness and favorable thermal and acoustic properties. On the other hand, a consortium of American automotive manufactures GM, Ford and Daimler-Chrysler [7] developed B-pillar structure, which was made of glass fibre. Their main intention was to reduce the vehicle weight with ultimately 60% of mass saving compared to a corresponding steel structure. In their work, B-pillar was analyzed under different loading conditions and exhibited competitive performance in comparison with the conventional solution.

In this paper, mechanical behavior of simplified form of composite T-joint in B-pillar (see Figure 1) is discussed thoroughly through experimental and numerical approaches. , Comparison of experimental and numerical results is presented. The influence of manufacturing process and experimental set-ups on

the load carrying capacity and failure mode of T-joint is discussed.

3. Modeling of Composite T-Joint

3.1 T-Joint profile

In order to perform a structural analysis of the T-joint, the FE code ABAQUS was chosen due to its convenient modelling technique for composite structures. The geometry profile was modelled with commercially available CAD software CATIA to get flexibility of design modification. As it has been stated in [8, 9 and 10], a portion of T-joint has been taken from an intersection point of B-pillar and longitudinal beam (the rocker), since the critical section that is subjected to critical load conditions compared with the rest of the B-Pillar structure is located at this point. Detailed dimensions of T-joint are shown in Fig. 1. The detailed geometry profiles of T joint was adapted from [8] with minor changes. In this case the shell thickness has been changed from 1.2mm to 2mm in order to get equivalent mechanical properties of composite material with steel material, which exhibits isotropic properties with higher values of stiffness. The laminate thickness was taken from the previous related work, [8]. The tube cross section is square with a dimension of 70 x 70 mm at the inner part.

3.2 Element Type selection

The choice of appropriate element type among the shell elements available in the code library depends on requirement of shell performance in the application area and level of accuracy of results. In this study, the T-joint is assumed to be a thin walled shell structure and is subjected to longitudinal loading with $\theta=0^\circ$, as shown in Figure 2.

ABAQUS code has several options of element types for shells. In this work the S4R shell element was chosen, which has both bending and membrane capabilities. In this shell element, both in-plane and normal loads are permitted. The element has six degrees of freedom at each node. S4R is a 4-node, quadrilateral, stress/displacement shell element with reduced integration and a large-strain formulation. In FEM analysis reduced integration provides significant reduction of running time.

4. Selection of composite fabric Weave type

Before starting to develop experimental modelling and perform a test, decision was made to select appropriate fabric weave style of the composite fabric on the base of their availability and properties.

There are three types of weave style widely known in fabric composite production; plain, twill, and satin, as shown in Fig. 3. In plain weave the weft is carried over all odd-numbered warps and under all even-numbered warps. For the next pass of the shuttle, the weft passes over the even-numbered warps, and under the odd. Sometimes it's two over and two under. Plain weave fabric has the advantage of giving strength in both directions but the disadvantage of halving the UD strength (since half the cloth is at 90°).

Generally, twill weaves are better than plain weaves when compound curved surfaces are manufactured. As shown in Fig. 3b. The twill is formed when the weft passes over warps 1 and 2 and under warps 3 and 4, and in the next pass, the shuttle of the loom passes over warps 2 and 3 and under warps 4 and 5. Twill weaves feel generally tighter, or more closely woven, than plain weaves.

In the satin weave, the weft floats or skips over as many as 12 warps before being woven in. The next pick repeats the float, but on a different set of warps. It can be seen in Fig. 3c that in satin fabrics labelled as a 5 harness - the weft floats over 4 warp threads. These are probably the best fabrics to use for complex moulds but can appear to be tightly woven and therefore difficult to wet out with resin. Since the threads have less crimping than plain and twill, satins make for the strongest use of the fibres.

From the above discussion and Table 1, plain woven type was chosen since the T-joint profile has not significantly complex shape. Beside, due to symmetrical rectangular cross-section of T-joint profile, stable and balanced weave was considered that led to select plain woven type.

5. T-Joint production and experimental setup

5.1 Material production

During the prototype design, detail manufacturing process was considered in order to take in account the detrimental effect of manufacturing process on the T-joint strength. Dimensional tolerances, design

of mold and ply layup mechanics were some of challenging problems in production of composite T-joint.

After the selection of fabric type, the first task was to model and produce appropriate mould to develop the desired T-joint profile. Because of the size of T-joint and its nature complexity during extraction process from the mould, bi-component T-joint mould was considered, as shown in Fig. 4.

To be more economical and reliable in preparation of test prototypes, special attention was paid to select appropriate mould material that can be reused and give accurate dimensional tolerance during high temperature curing process inside autoclave. The mould material was set to be the same as that of the T-joint structure, carbon/epoxy composite. This material is a plain weave prepreg GG203PIMP530R-42 supplied by Umeco plc, England, and used by EXP s.r.l, Italy. The matrix type is epoxy resin and it is developed for automotive sector. It is characterized by good impact resistance properties, quality surface finish and particularly suitable for high speed cold stamping. The resin content is $42\pm 3\%$.

After production of the mould, to achieve high grade surface finish, the mould was cleaned with Chem Cleaner in order to remove all traces of solvent-soluble contaminants such as waxes, silicones, oils, etc. Then after, Chemlease® MPP 712 EZ which acts as a sealant was used to coat the mould surface and cured for about 3 hours at room temperature. After curing, Chemlease® mold release was applied to remove easily the finished specimens from the mould.

At this stage, the required numbers of wetted plies were cut using numerical control cutting machine for each side of T-joint and assigned in their respective locations according to desired stacking sequence, (0/90)₅, as shown in Fig. 7.5a-d.

The T-joint laminate was produced from 10 plain woven fabrics with a laminate thickness of 2mm after polymerization.

Then, to avoid voids and entrapped air inside wet prepeg, the mould was covered with vacuum plastic bag and subjected to vacuum pressure of 0.98bar. Then after, it was put into the autoclave and

underwent through the prescribed curing cycle, Fig. 5f.

5.2 Fixture production

The fixture was constructed with cold rolled mild steel plates and aluminium blocks. It mainly consists of four components: the longitudinal slider, T-joint fixtures, fixed end supporters and cubic blocks placed inside the T extremities and are devoted to avoid local buckling at load application points. The main purpose of longitudinal slider was to support the whole T-joint fixture and allow it to move in the desired longitudinal direction, as shown in Fig. 6. After assembling the T-joint on the vertical fixture, its fixed ends were clamped by metallic plates fastened with bolted joints in order to apply uniform pressure around the circumference. Then, the whole testing fixture was mounted on Zweck Roell 100 mechanical testing machine which has a maximum loading capacity of 100kN, as shown in Fig. 6b.

5.3 Instrument setup

Fig.7 shows longitudinal bending experimental setup of T-joint that was built inside the laboratory to verify the simulation results. Rectangular rosettes (EK-06-250RD-10C/L type), by Vishay Micro-Measurements, were used in the experiment.

Each rosette consists of three strain gages oriented in 0°, 45° and 90° direction; i.e rosette 1 consists of strain gage 1(SG1), SG2 and SG3, as shown in Fig. 8. These rectangular rosettes were bonded on critical regions of T-joint using rapid adhesive, Z70, supplied by of HBM. Three rosettes were located at the top surface of T-joint, and the remaining two rosettes were located at the bottom surface of T-joint. The rosettes were connected to CANHEAD CB1014 module amplifier system (HBM), as shown in Fig. 7. To capture signal data and follow up the test, HBM MGCpluss DAQ was utilized, connected to the main server, where Catman Easy program is installed. Using this program data were captured, visualized and elaborated to understand the stress levels at critical locations. Fig. 6b and Fig. 8 show the loading point and the rosettes layout on T-joint, respectively.

On the other hand, the mechanical actuator of universal testing machine was electronically controlled to perform constant velocity tests at

0.5mm/s. Triggering threshold was set inside Catman Easy program and coupled to the universal testing machine to synchronize instruments, HBM MGCplus DAQ and universal testing machine load sensor.

5.4 Material Characterization

A T-joint prototype was cut to get specimens for tensile, compressive and shear tests according to ASTM standard procedures, as shown in Fig. 9. Specimens were cut from the lamina along fibre direction, in particular along 0° (warp), to determine the tensile and compressive strengths, and the elastic modulus of the material. Additional specimens were cut along 45° direction to determine the shear strength and shear modulus of the material. For each type of test we used five specimens to verify the consistency of found results of both cut specimens and ad hoc manufactured specimens. Tests were done on servo-hydraulic testing machine (INSTRON-8801) with a capacity of 100 kN. The machine was equipped with a standard load cell and a crosshead displacement measuring device. During the mount phase of the specimen, the maximum applied load was controlled and set lower than 0.2 kN in order to avoid specimen damage.

The strain gages were mounted at the centre of the specimen to measure the strain histories during test. Latest National Instrument Ethernet based strain gage module was utilized to acquire data, as shown in Fig. 10. The test data that include load and crosshead position were acquired using analog digital signal convertor, NI DAQCard-6062E. All data were acquired with a sampling rate equal to 1 kHz. To take under control the effect of thermal induced strain, half bridge circuit was implemented, even though the test time and speed were comparatively small in quasi-static test.

After a careful analysis, it was noticed that most of the obtained material characteristics are similar to properties of twill CFS003/LTM25 carbon-epoxy prepreg, except the shear rigidity. Plain weave fabric used in T-joint production has the highest shear rigidity compared with other weaves. This observation is quite agreed with the common knowledge that there is more yarn-to-yarn interlacing in fabrics with smaller weave floats [11].

Detailed material properties of plain weave carbon epoxy are shown in Table 2.

6. Results

6.1 Test Results

Fig. 11 shows the load-displacement curves of two T-joints subjected to bending load at the constant crosshead speed of 0.5mm/sec. The average maximum failure load was 9.94kN. As it can be clearly seen in the Figure 10, test-1 exhibited a slightly lower maximum failure load and lenient stiffness at initial stage during experimental test. After thorough investigation of failure modes of tested specimen-1 using pre-test taken pictures and recorded video, results revealed that loosely tighten bolts and fixture-T-joint slippage at the beginning of the test led to increase the displacement of T-joint at load application points for a given applied load. To avoid these problems, in the subsequent test, bolts were better tightened and test procedure was changed from single phase to multiple phases test procedure. In multiple phase test procedure, the machine was programmed to perform the test in sequential manner (applying the load up to 2kN, then return to its initial position, and then finally perform the test up to failure). It can be clearly seen in Fig. 11 that experimental test-2 exhibited linear load displacement curve from the very beginning and slightly lower displacement with a greater maximum failure load prior to catastrophic failure.

Fig. 12 shows strain-time and load-time curves in critical points, point 3, 6, and 9, as shown in Fig. 8. Most strain values were increased linearly, similar to the applied load. High strain value was found at critical location, point 9, near to the edge. In both tested prototypes, the initial cracks was observed at the top section of T-joint, which is subjected to tensile loading, as indicated by 1 in Fig. 13, and then it was extended rapidly to other regions, as indicated by 2 in Fig. 13. At initial stage, the dominant failure was matrix crack and delamination along the junction line of top and side surfaces of T-joint. This is due to the fact that plies were prepared independently for each four sides of T-joint, as shown in Fig. 5a-d. Thus, the only means to integrate those adjacent plies was the resin matrix. The resin acted as adhesive to join the plies at the edges. Therefore, the strength around these localized

areas was mainly related to the resin properties as well as manufacturing process. Starting from 90% of failure load the dominant failure observed during the test was rapid fibres fracture propagated along direction 2 prior to catastrophic failure.

6.2 Comparison of test result and FEM simulation results

Experimentally observed failure regions were predicted well by FEM analysis as highly stressed zones. In particular, the stress analysis indicated that at the curved part of the T-joint, near to edges, critical stress was observed. When comparing the normal stress to the ply strength properties (Table 2), it was observed that the local failure was well predicted, as shown in Fig. 14. As it can be well seen in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14, experimentally found failure zone was well predicted using FEM stress analysis. Moreover, the calculated shear stress from FEM at the critical location (78MPa), point 9 in Fig. 8, is quite good agreement with the shear strength of outer layer of ply (84MPa).

7. Conclusion

In this paper, behaviour fabric carbon/epoxy composite T-joint subjected to bending loading was investigated using experimental and numerical methods. Main found results are summarized as follow:

- From the test results, it can be clearly seen that in both experimental testes crack initiation and propagation were well identified at critical points, at the edge of fillet section of T-joint. The type failure at beginning of the test was dominated by the matrix crack propagation along the edge for some a while. Then, it was followed by fibre breakage at the top surface and extended to the bottom surface of T-joint. The fibre breakage was caused by tensile loading at the top surface.
- The experimental test results illustrated that the manufacturing process and experimental set-ups influence the performance (the load carrying capacity) and failure mode of T-joint, i.e. due to discontinued plies layup at each side of T-joint profile, premature matrix crack and delamination were observed at the edges which, consequently, affected the failure mode and maximum load.

- The measured strain at critical points indicated that the stress level at edge, i.e. at rosette 3, is higher by one order of magnitude than the stress level at the middle, rosette 1.
- Finite element analysis predicted well the stress distribution and failure stress of the critical regions observed during experimental tests.

From experimental and numerical results it can be concluded that appropriate numerical simulation can be considered as a effective tool to study the performance of automotive structural joints without developing physical prototypes.

8. References

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Fig. 1. Illustrative example of sectioned T-joint from B-pillar

Fig. 2. Geometry profile of T joint with load application at the reference point.

Fig. 3. Types of weave stays

Fig. 4. T-joint mould

Fig. 5. Manufacturing process of T-joint

Fig. 6. Experimental setup: a) CAD model; b) Experimental model.

Fig. 7 Experimental setup for T-joint test.

Fig. 8 Orientation of three-grid rectangular rosettes, type EK-06-250RD-10C/L.

Fig. 9. Location of test specimens for material properties of T-joint.

Fig. 12. Strain-time and Force-time curves.

Fig. 10. Experimental setup for composite specimen

Fig.13 Crack initiation and propagation mode

Fig.11. Load displacement curves

Fig. 14. Maximum principal stress distribution.

Table 1 Comparison of Weave style [13]

<i>Weave type</i>	<i>Durability</i>	<i>Stability</i>	<i>Balance</i>
Plain	Poor	Good	Good
Twill	Good	Moderate	Moderate
Satin	Excellent	Poor	Poor

Table 2. Material properties of Composite plain carbon-epoxy fabric prepreg

Properties	Values
Young modulus in longitudinal direction	52.15 GPa
Young modulus in transverse direction	55.15 GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.059
Shear modulus ¹²	4.14 GPa
Longitudinal tensile strength	618 MPa
Transverse tensile strength	652 MPa
Longitudinal compressive strength	642 MPa
Transverse compressive strength	556 MPa
In plane shear strength	84 MPa